

A REVIEW OF MUSHROOM DIVERSITY

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Abstract

The plump, spore-bearing fungal fruit body that develops on soil above ground or another substrate is called a mushroom. A study was undertaken on the mushroom diversity of India. It is found that different types of mushrooms grow in various localities in different seasons. Some species are edible and some are nonedible to man. They have rich medicinal and nutritional values. They act as a means for the degradation of biomass for the recycling of nutrients. In the present study, the author could enumerate a total of 127 species found in different regions of India. The majority of them belong to the division Basidiomycota.

Keyword: Mushroom; Diversity; India; Edible; Nutritional

Introduction:

There has been global research on the diversity of fungi. Around 1.5 million different types of fungi have been identified thus studies of fungal diversity have been conducted worldwide (Crous, 2006; Hawksworth, 2004). The 50% have been described (Monoharachary et. al., 2005). India has 27,000 different types of fungi. A significant biological and monetary impact is made by wild mushrooms. Because of their texture and delectable flavor, they have likely been ingested by man with care from the dawn of time. The nine crucial amino acids for humans are present in the mushroom proteins, along with the majority of non-essential amino acids and amides that are naturally occurring (Chang and Miles, 2004). Their high protein, vitamin, mineral, fiber, and trace element content, along with low to nil calorie and cholesterol content, give them a rich nutritional value. Since ancient periods, numerous of them have been used in folk medicine. Effective nutraceuticals, or substances having medical and nutritional qualities that are taken as medications in the form of pills or capsules rather than food, are produced by some of them. Others can produce neutraceuticals, which are natural foods that may be useful in promoting human health and strengthening the immune system. They are the origins of an extensive variety of bioactive compounds,

including those with anti-HIV, cytotoxic, hypocholesterolemic, antidiabetic, antiviral, antibacterial, antioxidant, antiparasitic, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antiproliferative, and antitumor properties.

The second most diverse group is fungi, which is also a key component of supplementary "mega-diverse" groupings similar to bacteria, insects, nematodes, and arachnids. There are thought to be 5.1 million 6-8 different species of fungi, there are more than 27,000 species of fungus in India. One of the most significant categories of eukaryotic organisms is the fungus, which is widely recognized for creating a wide variety of new metabolites that are either employed as medications directly or as prime structures for artificial alterations (Kock *et al.*, 2005).

Heterotrophic creatures with a wide range of morphology, size, physiology, and reproduction are called fungi. Truffles, mushrooms, and puffballs were adored by the ancient Greeks and Romans, as well as their less refined peers. The body of the mushroom is enough big to be harvested by finger and visible with the unaided eye (Anon 2005). The morphology of mushrooms is quite variable and varied. Distinct variations in cap and stem dimensions, hue, feel, and form are evident characteristics that are crucial for identifying mushrooms. The fact that certain mushrooms are toxic and others are edible makes a significant distinction between them. Worldwide mycologists have produced extensive documentation on the systematic description of macrofungi. By ancient times, mushrooms were a part of the diets of the Greeks and Romans. Chinese people viewed them as the elixir of life, whereas Romans saw them as the meal of the gods (Bashir *et al.* 2014). Wild edible mushrooms have long been used in many nations as scrumptious and nourishing meals and remedies (Saiqa *et al.* 2008).

The fruiting body of a fungus's reproductive structure is referred to as its "fungus". Unlike bacteria, plants, and animals, fungi are members of the fungal kingdom. Fungi and other plants frequently coexist in symbiosis, usually near the roots of certain trees, where both entities benefit from the association. Both wild and farmed mushrooms, especially those found in forests, are used in commercial mushroom cultivation. The species that arise via culture are all saprobes, or decomposers, capable of finishing their life cycle using decomposing organic materials. The majority of mushrooms that are harvested from forests are ectomycorrhizal, meaning that they can only produce fruit when they coexist with a live fungus on host trees.

Das *et al.* 2010 elaborate that the Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fruiting bodies are referred to as fungi in general, but this name only refers to a brief stage of the reproductive life cycle of these organisms. The fungus can be plucked by hand, be bulky adequate to be seen with the unaided eye, and be either epigenous or hypogenous. Mostly basidiomycetes, but also some ascomycetes, are the taxonomic group of fungi that create mycelium. It is believed that there are 140,000 species of fungus on Earth, of which 10%, or around 14,000, are known. Around 7,000 species of mushrooms remain unexplored that, if found, may be beneficial to mankind (Hawksworth, 2001). This is based on the assumption that the percentage of helpful mushrooms between the unexplored and unstudied mushrooms is just 5%. Fungi have long been associated with humanity and have a thoughtful biological and economic effect. Remote mushrooms have been eagerly eaten by gentlemen meanwhile antique times, undoubtedly because of their pleasant taste (Das *et al.* 2010). According to Agahar Murugkar and Subbulakshmi (2005) and Wani *et al.* (2010), they have a huge nutritional value and are rich in protein, vitamins, trace elements, minerals, fiber, and

minimal or no cholesterol and calories. Since ancient times, several of them have been utilized in traditional medicine. Some of these are natural foods called nutraceuticals, which may be useful for boosting the body's immune system and preserving health, while others can yield potent nutrients, which are substances with nutritional and medicinal qualities that are taken as medicine as tablets or capsules rather than as diet (Elmastas *et al.*, 2007; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2007). Antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, antioxidant, antiparasitic, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antiproliferative, antitumor, anti-HIV, anti-cytotoxic, hypocholesterolemic, antidiabetic, anticoagulant, hepatoprotective compounds, etc. are just a few of the many bioactive substances that are known to be abundant in mushrooms (Lindequist *et al.*, 2005; Ajith and Janardhanan, 2007). Approximately 650 of the 14,000 acknowledged species have therapeutic qualities, and 2,000 of them are suitable for ingestion by humans (Rai *et al.*, 2005). Because many edible and medicinal mushrooms are beneficial to the growth of human health in the form of food, medication, minerals, and medicine, mushrooms are a godsend for development in the domains of diet, remedy, and unemployment in developing nations with high biodiversity, such as India, in addition to others. Sheena *et al.* (2005), Rai *et al.* (2005), and Wani *et al.* (2010). The diversity of Indian mushrooms, their therapeutic and nutritional value for health, and the advantages of different Indian mushrooms as food, medicine, minerals, etc. are all covered in this review. Global mycologists have produced extensive documentation about the systematic description of macrofungi.

India has diverse soils and climatic conditions. Twenty-one agroecological zones exist, ranging from the hills in the north-south coasts, and the desert in the west-east to the huge rainfall regions. Due to its varied agroclimatic surroundings and plentiful cultivated waste, India has been manufacturing mushrooms primarily for its use for over 40 years. Evidence from archaeology links edible species to human habitation in Chile before 13,000 years nonetheless, the use of forest mushrooms was first documented in China before numerous centuries of the time of Christ. The commercial production and the establishment of several high-tech export-focused factories overseas. Nonetheless, small farms continue to produce the majority of mushrooms. Around the world, edible mushrooms constitute a delectable food source. Even in wealthy nations, the amount of remote edible mushrooms consumed is rising because of increased mindfulness of their significant protein and vitamins B, C, D, and micronutrient content. Almost twice as nutritious as fruits or vegetables, they are abundant in nutrients. Apart from dietary intake, there is ample proof that several species possess compounds that either avoid or minimize the likelihood of developing heart disease, cancer, diabetes, and viral infections. Fungi can produce various bioactive compounds that are usually associated with the mycelial cell wall and help improve resistance to carcinogens (Ramesh and Pattar, 2010). Functional foods that have been enhanced or altered and included in a normal diet to yield health advantages are known as nutrients. Foods made with mushrooms may be beneficial to health as well as being nutritious. Additionally, the mushroom may include antioxidants that are beneficial for treatment (Jayakumar *et al.*, 2006; Nitha *et al.*, 2010; Sudha *et al.*, 2008). In many regions of India, wild mushrooms are a widely used food and medicinal ingredient. With almost 283 wild mushroom species out of 2000 known worldwide, most Indian ethnic groups have rich and thorough traditional mycological knowledge. There have been several studies conducted on ethnomycological elements in India and throughout the world.

Significance of Mushroom:

The advantages of mushrooms to our bodies are numerous and profound. Including mushrooms in our diet regularly helps us stay immune to various ailments. Mushrooms are a tasty and wholesome complement to gluten-free nourishment, and like other vegetables and fruits, they are gluten-free. Numerous types of mushrooms include beta-glucans, which can have a role in physiological processes about the body's metabolism of fats and carbohydrates as well as immune-stimulating effects and allergy tolerance. According to Duyff (2006) and Rop *et al.* (2009), the most efficient beta-glucans are those found in shiitake, oysters, and split mushrooms. B vitamins, which assist in building energy by breaking down proteins, lipids, and carbs, are found in mushrooms and include riboflavin, niacin, and pantothenic acid (US Department of Agriculture *et al.*, 2009). Although mushrooms have little in fat, calories, cholesterol, and salt, they are high in numerous nutrients that are often found in cereals or animal products. Shiitake (*Lentinula edodes*): Used in cuisine all over the world, shiitake mushrooms are a common culinary ingredient. Lentin, the polysaccharide from which it gets its name, is one of the many health-promoting ingredients it contains. Because of its anticancer characteristics, lentinan has been isolated and is being utilized to treat gastric and additional cancers (Sasidharan *et al.*, 2010). In addition, shiitake mushrooms stabilize blood sugar, reduce atherosclerosis and platelet aggregation, and have antiviral properties (including against HIV, hepatitis, and the "flu"), antifungal, and antibacterial properties (Yamada *et al.*, 2002).

Mushroom diversity:

Countless species of Agaricaceae, frequently characterized by the type *Agaricus*, have been reported by Indian mycologists from various Indian states. Biodiversity surveys were carried out by several workers in diverse portions of Central India. About 33 percent of the world's mushroom variety is found in India. According to Manoharachary *et al.* 2005 among the 1.5 million fungi, only 50% have been identified so far. he reported diverse practices of medicinal mushrooms viz., *Pleurotus sp.*, *Lentinus sp.*, *Pisolithus sp.*, *Schizophyllum sp.*, *Agaricus bisporus*, *Pleurotus sp.* *Ganoderma lucidum*, *A. campestris*, and *Termitomyces heimii*. A huge quantity of *Agaricus* which embraces species of *Macrolepiota*, *Lepiota*, and *Leucocoprinus* were reported. Senthilarasu and Kumaresan in 2016 identified 60 genera with 132 species in it fitting to Agaricales, Russulales, and Polyporales. *Xylaria* species grow on divers of substrata, specifically barked timber, dung, and termite/ant nests (Rogers 2000, Hsieh *et al.* 2010, Karun and Sridhar 2015). The widespread *Ganoderma applanatum*, or shelf mushroom, is unique among all woody Polyporaceae fungi therefore instead of as a food is used as a medician (Acharya 2010). A total of 153 edible and medicinal mushrooms were reported by (Karwa and Rai 2010) in a study conducted in the Melghat forest in the Satpuda range of Maharashtra. The dominant species were *Pleurotus*, *Morchella*, *Termitomyces*, *Schizophyllum*, *Agaricus*, *Ganoderma*, *Cantharellus*, *Auricularia*, and others.

Ecology of mushrooms:

The majority of fungi, with mushrooms, are deep-rooted plant mycelium that filters pollutants out of the soil and functions as a natural recycler and sponge. By dissolving dead organic debris, plants, dead wood and trees, termite

combs, carrion, and leaf litter, they contribute to the creation of fresh nutrients and rich soil. Here, decaying stuff is broken down to generate new, making them nature's recyclers. For this reason, some fungi and bacteria aid nature in destroying the aged and deceased. Fungi are a complicated phenomenon that arises in natural ecosystems. Numerous variables, including rainfall, temperature, microclimate, soil, season, humidity, and exposure to microorganisms and plants, are associated with it. Under the influence of physiological and environmental variables, particularly appropriate temperature and humidity, fungi create fruiting bodies (Pradeep *et al.* 2003). The study of macrofungal diversity has benefited greatly from the efforts of several mycologists (Natarajan *et al.* 2005, Kaur *et al.* 2013). Senthilarasu and Kumaresan (2016) specifically examined the variety of agaric fungi in the Nilgiri Biosphere Reserve, Western Ghats, Tamil Nadu. They examined the morphological taxonomy of 15 species of agaricomycetes that were collected from Karnataka Western Ghats dipterocarp forests and belong to the order Agaricales. In addition to the species that are there, biodiversity also refers to the genetic variety of individual living forms, the diversity of populations within a species, and the widespread habitats and ecosystems that survive on Earth. Some types of plants and trees are linked to specific fungal species (Hawksworth, 2001). The biology, ecology, and economy of forest regions are all impacted in different ways by forest fungi. Species of fungi are markers of the health of forests. The observed variation in the existence of fungal species in different territories may be due to their special way of feeding, and macrofungi rising in the mud are symbiotic, saprophytic on rotten and dead wood, and parasitic on trees, and micro fungi have a cosmopolitan distribution. was also found (Suryanarayanan *et al.* 2004). Termitomyces grow symbiotically with termites as a valued antioxidant (Puttaraju *et al.* 2006). Basidiomycetes like *Schizophyllum* and *Xylaria* are rarely observed among flophytes on forest trees of Nilgiri Biosphere Reserve (Venkatesan 2004). Termite nests are one of the most important ecological niches of *Xylaria*, which is mainly due to the favorable microclimatic conditions of *Xylaria* (Guedebe *et. al.*s 2009).

Mushroom of Tropical region

In India, countless randomized experiments to document fungal diversity. In contrast to tropical nations like India, where there has been less research on mushrooms, Western countries have researched mushrooms extensively. According to Suryanarayanan *et al.* (2003), fungal variety is often more complex in tropical regions than in temperate zones. Studies of fungal diversity have been conducted in several regions of India, including Sikkim (Das 2010), Jammu and Kashmir (Kumar *et al.* 2011), Amarkantak Biosphere Reserve (Dwivedi *et al.* 2012), Bengaluru, Karnataka (Pushpa *et al.* 2012), Meghalaya (Khaund 2013), Nagaland (Kumar *et al.* 2013), kaj Länsi-Ghatini alad (Thiribhu *et al.* 2014). Karnataka (Kumaresan kaj Senthilarasu, 2016). The traditional and ethnomedical knowledge of mushrooms in West Bengal was documented by (Dutta *et al.* 2014). In the Kokrajhar area of Assam, the Bodo population uses edible wild mushrooms, as described by Basumatary and Gogai in 2016. Eleven edible mushroom species from the Shimla uplands were identified by Lakhanpal in 2014. In the state of Kerala, Kumar and Manimohan (2009) discovered a new species of *Leucocoprius*.

Mushroom diversity in India:

There is a total of 850 species (approximately) of fungi in India (Deshmukh, 2004). Indians used mushrooms for food and medicinal, according to the antique medical text Charaka Samhita (3000–500 BC). On the other hand, *Podaxis pistillaris* (L.: Pers.), which Koenig had collected and sent from the state of Tamil Nadu, was identified and described by Linnaeus in the 18th century, marking the beginning of the scientific study of fungus in India. Later, the English mycologist Revd M.J. For the Berkeley Publications Series Sir J.D. Hooker made a large collection, mostly from Assam, Khasi Hills, Darjeeling, and Sikkim. In India, the practice of gathering mushrooms and doing scientific research on them dates back to the 1800s (Kaul, 2002). Paul Henning made a substantial contribution to the second phase by describing an additional 32 genera and 68 species from India. The involvement of various Indian laborers in the research of higher fungi, in addition to European and American laborers, was a significant aspect of the second phase. Not to be overlooked is E. J.'s study on Indian fungus. Together with G.R. Bisby, Butler, who held the position of Imperial Mycologist in Pusa (Bihar), created the first comprehensive catalog of Indian fungus. Sarbhoy *et al.* provided an update for this article. During that time, two notable Indian professionals were Prof. K.S. Thind from the University of the Punjab in Chandigarh and Prof. S.R. Bose from Kolkata, West Bengal. India's edible mushroom business received a much-needed boost from the 3rd phase of work, which is believed to have commenced in the early 1970s and is still ongoing. Ever since, several investigators from all across India have persisted in their studies about the variety of mushrooms and their potential use as both food and medicine (Swapna *et al.*, 2008; Das, 2010, Sachan *et al.*, 2013). Region-wise details of fungal diversity surveys in India are tabulated in Table 1.

Conclusion:

India has a vast diversity of fungi especially, mushrooms. Mushrooms are medicinally and nutritionally very rich. To date, very few species have been identified. It is expected that many more species of mushrooms are yet to be explored which have the potential to open different avenues in medical science. Also, they can act as a rich source of nutraceuticals. Due to various man-made activities like forest fires, urbanization, industrialization, colonization, etc., many wild mushrooms are vanishing from the earth which should be protected and conserved.

Table 1: Region-wise fungal diversity of some parts of India

Sr. No	Name Of Macrofungi	Habitat	Division	Class	Order	Family
1.	<i>Agaricus argyropotamicus</i>	Garhwal district, Uttar Pradesh	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
2.	<i>Agaricus arvensis</i>	Baroda State	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
3.	<i>Agaricus augustus</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae

4.	<i>Agaricus campestris</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
5.	<i>Agaricus compestris</i>	West Bengal	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
6.	<i>Agaricus compestris</i>	Rajasthan	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
7.	<i>Agaricus heterocystis</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
8.	<i>Agaricus solidipes</i>	Garhwal district, Uttar Pradesh	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
9.	<i>Amanita muscaria</i>	Western Ghats	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Amanitaceae
10.	<i>Auricularia auricular</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Auriculariales	Auriculariaceae
11.	<i>Auricularia auricular-judae</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Auriculariales	Auriculariaceae
12.	<i>Auricularia delicata,</i>	Rajasthan	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Auriculariales	Auriculariaceae
13.	<i>Auricularia mesentrica,</i>	Rajasthan	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Auriculariales	Auriculariaceae
14.	<i>Boletus crocatus</i>	Baroda State	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Boletales	Boletaceae
15.	<i>Bovista nigrescens .</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
16.	<i>Calocybe indica</i>	West Bengal	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Lyophyllaceae
17.	<i>Calocybe indica</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Lyophyllaceae
18.	<i>Calvatia gigantean</i>	Western Ghats	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
19.	<i>Cantharellus aurantiacus</i>	West Bengal	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Cantharellales	Cantharellaceae
20.	<i>Cantharellus cibarius</i>	West Bengal	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Cantharellales	Cantharellaceae
21.	<i>Cantharellus cibarius</i>	Himachal Pradesh	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Cantharellales	Cantharellaceae
22.	<i>Cantharellus infundibulliformis</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Cantharellales	Cantharellaceae
23.	<i>Cantharellus minor</i>	Himachal Pradesh	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Cantharellales	Cantharellaceae
24.	<i>Cerioporus squamosus</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
25.	<i>Clathrus cancellatus</i>	Koka forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Phallales	Phallaceae
26.	<i>Clavaria rosea</i>	Karnataka	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Clavariaceae
27.	<i>Clavaria stricta</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Clavariaceae

28.	<i>Clavulina cristata</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Cantharellales	Clavulinaceae
29.	<i>Clavulina rugosa</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Cantharellales	Clavulinaceae
30.	<i>Clitocybe ectypoides</i>	Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Tricomycetes
31.	<i>Clitocybe nuda</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Tricholomataceae
32.	<i>Collybia butyracea</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Tricholomataceae
33.	<i>Coltricia perennis</i>	Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Hymenochaetales	Hymenochaetaeae
34.	<i>Conocybe tenera</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Bolbitiaceae
35.	<i>Coprinellus</i> sp.	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Psathyrellaceae
36.	<i>Coprinus comatus</i>	Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
37.	<i>Coprinus comatus</i>	Western Ghats	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
38.	<i>Coprinus comatus</i>	West Bengal	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
39.	<i>Coprinus</i> sp.	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
40.	<i>Cortinarius</i> sp	Western Ghats	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Cortinariaceae
41.	<i>Cystoagaricus trisulphuratus</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Psathyrellaceae
42.	<i>Daedaleopsis confragosa</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
43.	<i>Daldinia concentric</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Ascomycota	Sordariomycetes	Xylariales	Hypoxylaceae
44.	<i>Daldinia concentrica</i>	Tamil Nadu	Ascomycota	Sordariomycetes	Xylariales	Hypoxylaceae
45.	<i>Dictyophora duplicate</i>	Koka forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Phallales	Phallaceae
46.	<i>Fibroporia radiculosa</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Fomitopsidaceae
47.	<i>Ganoderma applanatum</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Ganodermataceae
48.	<i>Ganoderma lipsiense</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Ganodermataceae

49.	<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Ganodermataceae
50.	<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Ganodermataceae
51.	<i>Geaster fimbriatus</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Geastrales	Geastraceae
52.	<i>Geastrum triplex</i>	Karnataka	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Geastrales	Geastraceae
53.	<i>Gymnopilus junonius</i>	Western Ghats	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Hymenogastraceae
54.	<i>Helvella crispa</i>	Himachal Pradesh	Ascomycota	Pezizomycetes	Pezizales	Helvellaceae
55.	<i>Helvella emitra</i>	Himachal Pradesh	Ascomycota	Pezizomycetes	Pezizales	Helvellaceae
56.	<i>Hygrocybe parvula</i>	Karnataka	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Hygrophoraceae
57.	<i>Hygrocybe</i> sp.	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Hygrophoraceae
58.	<i>Hypholoma fasciolaria</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Strophariaceae
59.	<i>Hypholoma sublateritium</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Strophariaceae
60.	<i>Inocybe fraudans</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Inocybaceae
61.	<i>Lacterius affinis</i>	Koka forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Russulaceae	Russulaceae
62.	<i>Lenizites acuta</i>	Jalgaon	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
63.	<i>Lenizites elagans</i>	Jalgaon	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
64.	<i>Lenizites stereoides</i>	Jalgaon	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
65.	<i>Lentinus sajorcaju</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
66.	<i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
67.	<i>Lentinus subnudus</i>	West Bengal	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
68.	<i>Lentinus tuberregium</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
69.	<i>Lepiota Americana</i>	Koka forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
70.	<i>Leucoagaricus leucothites</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
71.	<i>Leucocoprinus brinbaumii</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
72.	<i>Lycoperdon echinatum</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae

73.	<i>Lycoperdon</i> Sp.	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
74.	<i>Macrolepiota procera</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
75.	<i>Macrolepiota procera</i>	Himachal Pradesh	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
76.	<i>Marasmius androsaceus</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Marasmiaceae
77.	<i>Marasmius cladophyllus</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Marasmiaceae
78.	<i>Marasmius delectans</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Marasmiaceae
79.	<i>Marasmius rotula</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Marasmiaceae
80.	<i>Melanoleuca grammopodia</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Tricholomataceae
81.	<i>Morchella angusticeps</i>	Himachal Pradesh	Ascomycota	Pezizomycetes	Pezizales	Morchellaceae
82.	<i>Morchella conica</i>	Himachal Pradesh	Ascomycota	Pezizomycetes	Pezizales	Morchellaceae
83.	<i>Morchella esculenta</i>	Himachal Pradesh	Ascomycota	Pezizomycetes	Pezizales	Morchellaceae
84.	<i>Morchella hybrid</i>	Himachal Pradesh	Ascomycota	Pezizomycetes	Pezizales	Morchellaceae
85.	<i>Mutinus raveneli</i>	Koka forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Phallales	Phallaceae
86.	<i>Mycena galericulata</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Tricholomataceae
87.	<i>Mycena</i> sp	Western Ghats	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Mycenaceae
88.	<i>Mycena</i> sp.	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Mycenaceae
89.	<i>Mycena</i> Sp.	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Mycenaceae
90.	<i>Panaeolus ephincitrinus</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Bolbitiaceae
91.	<i>Peziza badia</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Ascomycota	Pezizomycetes	Pezizales	Pezizaceae
92.	<i>Phellorina inquinans</i>	Rajasthan	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Phelloriniaceae
93.	<i>Pisolithus arhizus</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Boletales	Sclerodermataceae
94.	<i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i>	Baroda State	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Pleurotaceae

95.	<i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Pleurotaceae
96.	<i>Pleurotus sapidus</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Pleurotaceae
97.	<i>Pleurotus sajorcaju</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Pleurotaceae
98.	<i>Podaxis pistillaris</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
99.	<i>Polyporus albellus</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
100.	<i>Polyporus alreolaris</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
101.	<i>Polyporus arcularius</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
102.	<i>Polyporus elegans</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
103.	<i>Polyporus lucidus</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
104.	<i>Polyporus offinis</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
105.	<i>Polyporus versicolor</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
106.	<i>Russula delica</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Russulales	Russulaceae
107.	<i>Schizophyllum commune</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	agaricales	Schizophyllaceae
108.	<i>Schizophyllum commune</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Schizophyllaceae
109.	<i>Scleroderma bermudense</i>	Karnataka	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Boletales	Sclerodermataceae
110.	<i>Scleroderma citrinum</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Boletales	Sclerodermataceae
111.	<i>Scutellinia scutellata</i>	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Ascomycota	Pezizomycetes	Pezizales	Pyronemataceae
112.	<i>Termitomyces eurhizus</i>	West Bengal	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Lyophyllaceae
113.	<i>Termitomyces heimii</i>	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Lyophyllaceae

114	Termitomyces microcarpus	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Lyophyllaceae
115	Termitomyces microcarpus,	Rajasthan	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Lyophyllaceae
116	Termitomyces microspores	West Bengal	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Lyophyllaceae
117	Trametes versicolor	Western Ghats	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
118	Trametes versicolor	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Polyporaceae
119	Tremella mesenterica	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Tremellomycetes	Tremellales	Tremellaceae
120	Tricholoma equestre	Western Ghats	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Tricholomataceae
121	Tricholoma sp.	Western Ghats	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Tricholomataceae
122	Volvariella diplasia	Baroda State	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Pluteaceae
123	Volvariella speciosa	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Pluteaceae
124	Volvariella terastius	West Bengal	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Pluteaceae
125	Xanthagaricus Sp.	Tamil Nadu	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Agaricales	Agaricaceae
126	Xylaria hypoxylon	Tamil Nadu	Ascomycota	Sordariomycetes	Xylariales	Xylariaceae
127	Xylaria polymorpha	Koka and Chandpur forest Bhandara	Ascomycota	Sordariomycetes	Xylariales	Xylariaceae

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